

Survival and recovery of seedlings of different ages at 2 water depths. West Bengal, India.

seedlings left for 10 d more under saturated moisture to estimate recovery capacity.

Varieties differed significantly in initial height and leaf and tiller number. FR13A and FR43B were the tallest and had the most leaves in all age groups. In general, IR20 scored lowest for all characters, except it had the most tillers at 40 d old.

Highest survival of 10-d-old seedlings was in FR13A and CN716 at both flooding depths, followed by FR43B and CN717 (see figure). No IR20 plants survived the 60-cm water depth. All older seedlings of CN540 and FR43B survived.

Only CN716 showed complete recovery of younger seedlings at both water depths; 40-d-old seedlings surpassed both parents in 60 cm water. FR43B had good overall recovery at all seedling ages. No 10 d IR20 seedlings recovered; recovery otherwise increased gradually with seedling age.

Most varieties had higher elongation rates at 30 cm than at 60 cm water depth (see table). Ten-day-old CN540 seedlings had the highest elongation rate, FR43B elongated most in 30 cm and FR13A in 60 cm.

High initial height was correlated with low elongation rate in older seedlings

Elongation rate during submergence of 6 varieties at 10, 30, and 40 d old. West Bengal, India.

Variety	Elongation per d (%)					
	10 d old		30 d old		40 d old	
	30 cm	60 cm	30 cm	60 cm	30 cm	60 cm
CN540 (Suresh)	13.1	1.8	4.1	8.9	6.2	7.4
FR13A	2.6	3.1	5.0	5.6	1.4	5.2
FR43B	13.1	-1.4	2.8	1.9	5.9	1.4
CN716 (FR13A/CN540)	4.9	0.2	6.3	6.3	12.0	6.4
CN717 (FR43B/CN540)	2.5	1.5	4.6	3.0	5.1	6.6
IR20 (susceptible check)	10.1	dead	1.5	2.4	-4.9	-2.2

(-0.60 and -0.70 at 30 cm, and -0.81 and -0.73 at 60 cm water) but not with survival. Initial leaf number was positively correlated with survival only in 40-d-old seedlings at 60 cm water depth (0.60).

The resistant varieties can be divided into two groups: FR13A type and CN540 or FR43B type. FR13A type was more resistant at the heterotrophic stage (seedling surviving on endosperm), CN540 type was more resistant at the autotrophic stage (seedling producing its food).

Screening at both seedling stages could help identify resistance donors. Development of bridge parents such as CN716 (FR13A/CN540) that combine both types of resistance should lead to the production of genotypes with better flood tolerance. □

Adverse temperature tolerance

Screening criterion for cold tolerance at the seedling stage

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In the Yangtze valley in China, the first crop indica rice is sown in early Apr and transplanted in early May. Seedlings die when temperatures are abnormally low (6-10 °C for 5 d or longer). We investigated a screening criterion for cold tolerance at the seedling stage.

Table 1. Response of 5 rice varieties to low temperature (10/6 °C day/night) for 3, 7, 9 d. Hangzhou, China.

Variety	Response		
	3d	7d	9d
IR26	Tip of leaves rolled	All leaves into tubes or withered	Plant dead
Erjiufeng	Tip of leaves rolled	All leaves into tubes or withered	Plant dead
Biyuzaonuo	Normal	All leaves into tubes or withered	Plant dead
Reimei	Tip of leaves rolled	Tip of leaves rolled	All leaves rolled into tubes or withered
Zhonghua 8	Tip of leaves rolled	Normal	All leaves rolled

Table 2. Cold tolerance of 78 rice varieties at the 3-leaf stage. Hangzhou, China.

Tolerant	Ainanzao 39, Zaofengshou, Reimei, Fujikei 131, 81y4-5, Zhonghua 8, Fujikei 137, Akita 32, Wujiegu, Titanio, Yantouqing, Fujisaka 5, Fujikei 130, Longjiangdao.
Medium tolerant	Guiluai 8, Daguangxian, Leyi, Erjiulu 1, Qishirihuodao, Yuanfengzao, Wenzhouqing.
Medium	Zhenlong 13, Simei 2, Ejiunan 1, Chum 84-508, Eza 6, Zhuyunnuo, Yuan 2, Zaoxian 503, Zaolian 31, Fangyangu.
Medium susceptible	Zhenshan 97, Zaoxian 141, Wenge Zhong 83-49, Zhengui 51, Zuo 5 Zhuke 2, IR24, Huazaobai, Butuoai, ZRE8.
Susceptible	Ainanzao 1, Nongsheng, Jinke 5, Qingzhen 16, Hongtu 5, Hongtu 27, Fulianai, Fuyul, Qingganhuang Zhefu 802, Wenxuanqing, Biyuzaonuo, Luhongzao 1, Zhuxi 26, IR26, IR29, IR36, IR60, B3, Hongtu 31, Erjiufeng, Guangluai 4, Erjiuqing, Qingxiaojinzao, H1459, Junlianazao, Fu 8-1, Chaoyang 1, Aichang 25, Zhenyu, Guiluai 3, Erjiulong, Zaojianzaodao, Liantangzao, 5010, Xianfeng 1.

Seedlings of 5 varieties were grown in 50- × 20- × 15-cm plastic trays with 10 cm soil. At the 3- to 4-leaf stage they were subjected to low temperature (10/6 °C day/night) for 3, 7, and 9 d in the incubator. Incubation for 7 d was best for discriminating cold tolerance among varieties (Table 1).

Leaf rolling was the most visible abnormality and might be useful as a sensitive criterion of cold tolerance. It is more simple and practical than using leaf discoloration or dead seedling percentage.

We evaluated 78 varieties at the 3-leaf stage at 10/6 °C day/night for 7 d. The first leaf from the top rolled first, then the second leaf, then all leaves rolled or were fully withered. Varieties could be divided into five cold tolerance groups by leaf rolling symptoms (Table 2):

T = tolerant, all leaves normal
 MT = medium tolerant, tip to 1/2 of 1st leaf rolled (leaflet normal)

M = medium, 1/2 to 2/3 of 1st leaf rolled (leaflet normal)
 MS = medium susceptible, 1st and 2d leaves fully rolled (leaflet normal) or 1st leaf fully rolled
 S = susceptible, all leaves rolled or fully withered.

All of the eight japonicas tested were tolerant. Seven of the 12 tolerant indicas were traditional native varieties. Most of the recommended indica varieties were susceptible. Guiluai 8, Ainanzao 39, and Zaofengshou have been proposed as donors in developing cold-tolerant indica varieties. □

Effect of low temperature on selected rice varieties in Tanzania

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In the Usangu Plains in the south and Moshi and Mombo in the northeast,

low temperature affects the rice crop. Minimum temperatures below 15 °C from late Apr and Aug reduce yield if panicle initiation or heading occurs during the cool period.

We screened 65 Tanzanian varieties from the International Rice Germplasm Center collection for cold tolerance at seedling, panicle initiation, and anthesis (heading) stages in cold water tanks and in the IIRI phytotron.

Promising cold-tolerant Tanzanian rice varieties.

IRGC acc. no.	Variety	Score ^a at seedling stage	Spikelet sterility (%)	
			Panicle initiation	Anthesis
56208	ES076	3	–	17
56209	ES077 (Shingo)	3	–	–
06485	Afaa Kilombero 1-196	9	10	18
06481	Afaa Mwanza 1-104	9	19	78
56163	ES010 (Supa India)	9	18	16
56164	ES013	9	23	30
56181	ES040 (Turiani)	9	23	15
56184	ES043	9	24	38
56194	ES059 (Bishore)	9	16	13
56195	ES060 (Kialangawa)	9	22	63
56205	ES072	9	15	24
56210	ES078 (Zira)	9	19	–
56213	ES081 (Shindano)	7	17	–
06479	Gamti 1-34	9	37	15
06480	Afaa Mwanza 0-746	9	57	15
06491	Lindi Safari	9	77	6
56161	ES003	9	33	10
56167	ES018 (Gold)	9	26	13
56168	ES018 (Straw)	9	42	8
56183	ES042	7	30	9
56186	ES044 (Wahi)	9	60	13
56192	ES053 (Ringa)	9	–	3
56193	ES054	9	67	10
56214	ES082	9	60	12
07533	HR19	9	52	16

^aStandard evaluation system for rice score.